

Late Cenozoic left lateral strike-slip deformation in Minorca, Balearic Islands, Spain

Deformación direccional lateral izquierda durante el Cenozoico tardío en Menorca, Islas Baleares, España

C. Timoner¹, G. de Vicente^{2,3}, A. Olaiz⁴ and R. Díez-Fernández⁵

1 Facultad de Ciencias Geológicas, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, 28040 Madrid.ctimoner@ucm.es

2 GEODESPAL, F. C. Geológicas, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, 28040 Madrid.gdv@geo.ucm.es

3 Instituto de Geociencias IGEO, CSIC-UCM, 28040 Madrid

4 Repsol E&P, Madrid, Spain.antoniojose.olaiz@repsol.com

5 Departamento de Investigación y Prospección Geocientífica, Instituto Geológico y Minero. Calle de la Calera, 1, 28760 Tres Cantos, España. r.diez@igme.es

Abstract: *Minorca is located at the easternmost sector of the Betic orogen between N-S to NE-SW extensional basins. The elongate WNW-ESE shape of the island follows the strike of late high-angle faults, which parallel the North Balearic Fracture Zone (NBFZ). The structure of Minorca differs from that of other nearby Mediterranean islands and has been the subject of recent studies. In this work we report the results of a fault population analysis (including its cartographical projection) applied to three late WNW-ESE faults that cross the island longitudinally. The stress inversion results show a left-lateral movement with normal component for the Tramuntana Fault, with $R = 0,7$ and horizontal σ_1 and a normal movement with left-lateral component for the Mercadal and Binixems faults, with $R = 0,8$, vertical σ_1 and horizontal σ_2 ; in both cases there are structural and/or cartographical evidence of right-lateral deformation. These results explain several Alpine structures of the island, poorly interpreted up to now, but are unfitting for a solely right-lateral movement of NBFZ.*

Keywords: *Western Mediterranean, Alpine Orogeny, Strike-slip deformation belt, North Balearic Fracture Zone.*

Resumen: Menorca se encuentra en el extremo noroeste del orógeno Bético entre regiones sometidas a extensión y condirección N-S a NE-S. La estructura de la isla, caracterizada a grandes rasgos por una elongación ONO-ESE a favor de fallas modernas de alto ángulo paralelas a la Zona de Fractura del Norte de Baleares (NBFZ), difiere de la de otras islas de su entorno y ha sido objeto de estudios recientes. En este trabajo analizamos tres fallas tardías que cruzan la isla longitudinalmente mediante el set de inversión de esfuerzos y su proyección cartográfica. Los resultados de la inversión de esfuerzos implican un movimiento lateral-izquierdo con componente normal para la falla de Tramuntana, con $R = 0,7$ y σ_1 horizontal, y un movimiento normal con componente direccional para las fallas de Mercadal y Binixems, con $R = 0,8$, σ_1 vertical y σ_2 horizontal; en ambos casos encontramos evidencias estructurales y/o cartográficas de deformación lateral-derecha. Estos resultados permiten explicar varias estructuras Alpinas de la isla, hasta ahora vagamente interpretadas, aunque son incompatibles con un funcionamiento exclusivamente lateral-derecho de la NBFZ.

Palabras clave: Mediterráneo Occidental, Orogenia alpina, Cinturón de deformación direccional, Zona de Fractura del Norte de las Baleares

INTRODUCTION

The Balearic Promontory structure consists of a NE-SW fold and thrust belt with NW-directed tectonic transport affected by late NNE-SSW extension. This belt is located between extensional basins such as the Valencia Trough and the Algerian Basin. The tectonics of this region was controlled by the convergence between the Alboran block and the southern border of Iberia during the Betic Orogeny and by subsequent western Mediterranean dynamics. In this setting, Minorca island has a singular position close to the North Balearic Fracture Zone (NBFZ) and the Liguro-Provençal Basin.

Minorca differs structurally from other Alpine continental neighboring areas such as Majorca, Ibiza, Sardinia and

the Catalanian Coastal Ranges (Sàbat et al., 2018). Such differences arise from 1) basement-involved thick skinned tectonics; there are no relevant Carboniferous-Devonian basement outcrops in Majorca and Ibiza, and those of Sardinia and Catalonia are different from the Western Mediterranean Paleozoic complexes or Alkapeca (which seem to agree with the Minorcan succession; Bourrouilh, 2016); 2) A very penetrative NW-SE alpine faulting, as opposed to the main thrusting trends of Majorca and Ibiza that parallel the Betic ones; and 3) WNW-ESE late normal faults, different from those related to the NW-SE extension that formed the Valencia Trough.

The lack of detailed studies has resulted in a mostly descriptive understanding of the tectonics of Minorca. In this preliminary analysis, we focus on the regional faulting arrangement of the island, where WNW-ESE normal and strike-slip faults, parallel to the NBFZ, seem to predominate (Fig. 1A). The tectonic evolution of the western Mediterranean during the Cenozoic was controlled by the emplacement of the Tyrrhenian and Alboran arcs (e.g., Faccenna et al., 2014; Douwe et al., 2020). Therefore, the Minorca area should have acted as a right lateral transpressive deformation belt to accommodate (i) the easternwards movement of the Tyrrhenian subduction and (ii) the NW-directed thrusts of Majorca (Fig. 1). Nevertheless, most of the Cenozoic faults of Minorca define a left-lateral strike-slip deformation belt (Fig. 1A). We have used a population fault analysis to clarify this question. In order to do so, we mapped three major WNW-ESE faults

and collected in situ structural data around them. Field data were obtained from Tramuntana (TF), Mercadal (MF) and Binixems (BF) faults (Fig. 1A). We used (1) the Stress inverse package (Vavryčuk, 2014) based on Michael (1984) to obtain the relative orientation of principal axes and the magnitude of the stress tensor associated with a specific fault population (Fig. 1B), (2) plotted the P axis and (3) performed a slip model inversion to get the strain tensor. The new field and analytical data were integrated into previous cartographies.

Main structural features

Minorca is a WNW-ESE elongate island with an area of 700 km². Two different sectors can be distinguished: the Tramuntana block, formed mostly by Paleozoic and Mesozoic rocks, and the Migjorn block, which contains a

Fig. 1. A) Tectonic map of Minorca including main stress axes projection from the stress inversion and location of field data. Main faults are high-angle and strike WNW-ESE, parallel to the North Balearic Fracture Zone (NBFZ) and the elongation direction of the island. Sketches to the right show a tectonic evolution derived from the stress inversion results. FT: Ferragut Thrust, PT: Pregonda Thrust, TF: Tramuntana Fault, MF: Mercadal Fault, BF: Binixems Fault. Fault-slickensides data were collected at the locations indicated by stars. B) Fault population analysis projection of the Stress Inversion, the P Axes, and the Dey from the Slip Model (maximum horizontal shortening) from the Tramuntana Fault ($n=25$), the Mercadal Fault ($n=21$), and the Binixems Fault ($n=38$).

Miocene basin. The structural style of the island is multi-pronged. The basement of the island shows foliation and was primarily configured during the (Devonian-Carboniferous) Variscan Orogeny, while tectonic inversion of Permian-Triassic normal faults and a complex Alpine evolution entailed a set of WNW-ESE high-angle faults and NE-SW to NW-SE thrusts (Fig. 1A).

Variscan deformation and processes in Minorca are poorly documented. Paleozoic rocks crop out in the easternmost and central areas, along the cores (intrados) of open, nearly-upright antiforms. Variscan deformation resulted in an assemblage of West-verging compressional N-S structures, such as the Ferragut Thrust and several N-S to NNE-SSW normal faults that opened fluvial-alluvial (late Variscan) Permian basins. Ferragut Thrust (Fig. 1A) crops out in the middle of the island and transported Devonian strata onto

Carboniferous rocks. Its fault zone is featured by variably deformed rocks that have experienced more strain than any other rocks in the island. This thrust was reactivated during the Cenozoic and could have played an important role in the nucleation of Alpine thrusts and strike-slip faults.

Minorca had a complex evolution during the Alpine Orogeny. A logical set of Alpine structures and processes would include: 1) reworking/reactivation of previous Variscan structures; westwards to the Ferragut Thrust, NE-SW Alpine compression induced the Pregonda Thrust and reversed a normal late Variscan fault; 2) development of NW-SE trending folds close to high-angle WNW-ESE faults; and 3) formation of a set of WNW-ESE (strike-slip to normal) faults that crosses along the island. Bourrouilh (1983) described these faults as local strike-slip Alpine faults, whereas Sàbat et al. (2018) interpreted them as normal

Fig. 2. Macar de Sa Llosa pull-apart basin: an alluvial-lacustrine conglomerate deposit related to the sinistral transtensive zone of the Tramuntana Fault with a progressive unconformity (right).

faults related to the opening of the Liguro-Provençal Basin. Furthermore, this WNW-ESE high-angle faults are parallel to the NBFZ: a right-lateral transform fault that subjected the rotation of the Corsica-Sardinian block and the opening of Liguro-Provençal Basin (Romani et al., 2016; Faccenna et al., 2014; van Hinsbergen et al., 2020).

RESULTS

Stress inversion

The fault population analysis has been performed on pairs of slickenside-fault plane data ($n=25$ for TF, $n=21$ for MF and $n=38$ for BF). Results are represented from each fault in Figure 1B, and interpreted in the geological map of Figure 1A.

Tramuntana Fault

Slicing through the northern capes of the Island, such as Cavalleria Cape, Fornells and Cala Pudent area, Tramuntana Fault forms the northernmost structure of the Balearic Promontory, probably offshore extended. The results of stress inversion show a $R = 0,7$ with a horizontal σ_1 that implies a left-lateral strike-slip movement on the fault with some normal component. Slip Model results mainly fit with this solution, but some data could indicate a right-lateral fault displacement. Tramuntana Fault gives rise to the Macar de Sa Llosa pull apart (Fig. 2) which is compatible with the overall left-lateral deduced movement (Fig. 1A).

Mercadal Fault

Cropping out over the center of Tramuntana block, Mercadal Fault runs from Cala Morell to Illa d'en Colom, parallel to the Tramuntana Fault. The results of stress inversion have an $R = 0,8$ with a vertical σ_1 and an ENE trending and horizontal σ_2 . Therefore, the fault moved as a normal fault with a slight left-lateral component, parallel to the dip of the southern slope of El Toro mountain and to the wide southernmost blind normal fault movement that splits the Migjorn and Tramuntana blocks. In a broad view,

Mercadal Fault forms an anastomosed deformation zone that includes Binixems Fault area. Cartographically, near Mercadal area, Mercadal Fault appears to be a left-lateral strike-slip fault, whereas in Binixems Fault area it seems to be right-lateral.

Binixems Fault

Northwards from Alaior, near Mercadal Fault, Binixems Fault represents the east prolongation of Mercadal Fault. The results of stress inversion show an $R = 0,7$ with a vertical σ_1 and a horizontal NNE trending σ_2 , which indicate a mainly normal movement of the fault. As in Tramuntana, some few solutions from are compatible with a right-lateral movement.

Macar de Sa Llosa pull-apartbasin

Normal fault-related conglomerates of Macar de Sa Llosa (Fig. 2), near Son Parc, are the best studied example of late extension in Minorca. The deposit has been interpreted as upper Oligocene alluvial fans that drained its sediment from a lacustrine environment (Martín-Closas y Ramos, 2005) into a half-graben basin related to a Keuper detachment of the northwards antiform (Sàbat et al., 2018). Conversely, based on our results from Tramuntana fault dynamics, the Macar de Sa Llosa infilling deposit is due to the opening of a pull-apart between Tramuntana Fault releasing steps with two normal faults bordering the narrow basin (Fig. 2). Stress inversion results and this tectonic arrangement indicate an overall left-lateral transtensive deformation in Minorca island during the Miocene.

DISCUSSION

The stress inversion results are consistent with the structural setting in a model that emphasizes late Cenozoic left-lateral to normal displacements, even though the evolution of the WNW-ESE strike-slip faults must have been complex because: 1) although NBFZ is considered a right-lateral transform fault subject to the rotation of Corsica-Sardi-

nian block, the largest NBFZ-parallel faults of the Minorcan block do not solely agree with a right-lateral behavior; and 2) even though the left-lateral fault set matches with several Alpine structures such as the NW-SE thrusts and folds, even more than the expected right-lateral movement, a straight left-lateral role do not completely explain the Alpine tectonics of the island. For the moment, the Minorcan structure can be understood as an interaction between the outermost prolongation of the Betic orogen and the NBFZ transform dynamics, with a late general extension that overprinted previous WNW-ESE movements. This inversion in the directional displacements could be related to the westernmost part of the back arc extension of the Tyrrhenian subduction and the extension related to the opening of the Valencia Trough (Fig. 1A). These considerations mean that the Alpine evolution of Minorca will continue to be a hard-to-solve problem that remains prior to future studies, where the spatial and temporal relations between the tectonic events of the Western Mediterranean, such as the relative position of Minorca and Sardinian retro-arc evolution towards NBFZ, and the local deformation of Minorca will be the key questions.

REFERENCES

- Borrouilh R. (1983). *Estratigrafía, sedimentología y tectónica de la isla de Menorca y el Noreste de Mallorca (Balears)*. Tesis doctoral, Ministerio de Industria y Energía, Memorias del Instituto Geológico y Minero de España 99, 672 p.
- Bourrouilh R. (2016). The Balearic Islands in the Alpine Orogeny. *Boletín Geológico y Minero* 127 2/3, 527-546.
- Faccenna, C., Becker, T.W., Auer, L., Billi, A., Boschi, L., Brun, J.P., Capitanio, F.A., Funiciello, F., Horvath, F., Jolivet, L., Piromallo, C., Royden, L., Rossetti, F. and Serpelloni, E. (2014). Mantle dynamics in the Mediterranean. *Reviews of Geophysics* 52, 283–332.
- Martín-Closas C. and Ramos E. (2005). Palaeogene Charophytes of the Balearic Islands (Spain). *Geological Acta* 3, 39-58.
- Michael, A.J. (1984). Determination of stress from slip data: Faults and folds. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 89, 11517-11526.
- Sabat F., Gelibert B. and Rodriguez-Perea A. (2018). Minorca, an exotic Balearic island (Western Mediterranean). *Geologica Acta* 16, 411-426.
- Romani, P., Aslanian, D., Rabineau, M., Leroux, E., Gori, C., Silenziario, C., Blanpied, C. and Rubino, J. (2016). The Minorca Basin: a buffer zone between the Valencia and Liguro-Provençal Basins (NW Mediterranean Sea). *Terra Nova* 28, 245-256.
- van Hinsbergen, D.J.J., Torsvik, T.H., Schmid, S.M., Mañenco, L.C., Maffione, M., Vissers, R.L.M., Gürer, D. and Spakman, W. (2020). Orogenic architecture of the Mediterranean region and kinematic reconstruction of its tectonic evolution since the Triassic. *Gondwana Research* 81, 79-229.
- Vavryčuk, V. (2014). Iterative joint inversion for stress and fault orientations from focal mechanisms. *Geophysical Journal International* 199, 69-77.